

IPBES TCA Chapter 2. DMR 2.7 Visions from Indigenous and local knowledge/IPBES transformative change assessment

Versioning:4.0.0

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13926219

Project leaders: Helen Wheeler (helen.wheeler@aru.ac.uk)

Researchers

Geraud Tasse (geraudtasse@yahoo.fr)

Vera Helene Hausner (vera.hausner@uit.no)

Lelani Mannetti (lelani.mannetti@gmail.com)

Sandra Waddock (sandra.waddock@bc.edu)

Sebastian Villasante (sebastian.villasante@usc.es)

Timothee Fouqueray (timothee.fouqueray@uqo.ca)

Peter Bates (p.bates@unesco.org)

Data curator(s): Laurence Perianin (laurence.perianin@umontpellier.fr)

Description: The review corresponds to the IPBES transformative change assessment. The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 2 should address Visions of a sustainable world – for nature and people. The chapter provides evidence on Indigenous and local knowledge. In this context, a review of visions for a sustainable world for nature and people focused on the visions of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities was conducted and is further described below.

Process overview

Protocol

Given that each Indigenous People and local community has its own culture, needs and aspirations, project leader adopted a regional approach to compiling information on Indigenous Peoples' and local communities' visions of the desired future for people and nature. Through an invitation to contribute, knowledge and information were sought from contributors who were either holders of Indigenous and local knowledge, or experts in Indigenous and local knowledge (Hill et al., 2020). In many cases, authors played both roles. Although not exhaustive, the list provides a good geographical breakdown.

Step 1: initial list of contacts

Description: A preliminary list of contacts was drawn up based on the experts' knowledge. The main objective was to receive input from Indigenous and local knowledge holders and experts in Indigenous and local knowledge. An active effort was made to seek representation in the various regions, purposely seeking suggestions in areas where few people had been identified. The main criteria for selecting contributors were to include knowledge from people with close ties to Indigenous Peoples and local communities, either through membership of these communities, or through very close links with them.

Method: Expert knowledge

Search Date: Ongoing from 5/12/2023 to 07/05/2024

Number of contacts identified: 43 potential contributors

Location of the Data: Data collected is confidential so as not to share personal information without consent.

Step 2: reach-out through individual invitation to contribute

Description: A total of 43 potential contributors were contacted individually with an invitation to contribute (A) translated into French, Spanish, Norwegian and Russian. This process was iterative, as gaps in regional coverage were identified, attempts were made to fill them.

Method: outreach email campaign

Date of the outreach: 31/05/2023 to 5/12/2023

Location of the Data: Data collected is confidential so as not to share personal information without consent.

Step 3: compilation of the responses

Thirteen contributions were received. Some people agreed to contribute but were unable to do so for reasons of their own. This highlights the difficulties encountered by some, despite their intention to contribute, which limit their ability to get involved in this type of process. The research team should also acknowledge those who would have chosen not to contribute and thereby reflect that our contributors are a subset of experts in this area, who are willing to contribute to IPBES processes. Those who provided information in response to the invitation to contribute were invited to participate in the IPBES transformative change assessment as contributing authors (IPBES defined status).

Once responses had been received, written answers to the questions and supporting references (where available) were collated. The text of the responses to the questions was used to identify key thematic areas related to the three questions below:

- Why are visions important?
- What are the visions of desirable futures?
- How well does the concept of “visions of transformative change for nature and people” resonate?

These questions differ slightly from the initial questions sent out in the invitation to contribute, but they reflect the areas in which contributors provided the most information and probably reflect the questions that resonated most with contributors. The text relating to each theme was then used to draft responses to these questions and, in the case of the question “What are the visions of a desirable future?”, to develop the explanation of emerging themes. Respondents only provided references to written documents related to the issue of key resources relevant to the questions. These documents were reviewed where available and used to develop each part of the section of the text on the visions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities.

Location of the Data: the data is confidential as outlined in the invitation to contribute(A)

Step 4: validation by respondents (contributing authors)

The text was then returned to contributing authors to allow review and editing and further text alterations were made, references added, and changes were made to best reflect the content provided. In some cases, contributors had differing views and, in these cases, where possible, the diversity of views were represented. For authors that had submitted edits where there were questions of wording these were sent back for further review and clarification. This information was used in section 2.3.4.

Location of the Data: the data is confidential as outlined in the invitation to contribute.

References

Hill, R., Adem, Ç., Alanguai, W.V., Molnár, Z., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Bridgewater, P., Tengö, M., Thaman, R., Yao, C.Y.A., Berkes, F. and Carino, J., 2020. Working with Indigenous, local and scientific knowledge in assessments of nature and nature’s linkages with people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 43, pp.8-20.

Definition of files

ID	Names	File Type	Size	Description
1	1-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.7_ILK visions_V2	PDF		DMR
2	2-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.7_ILK visions_process	jpeg		Process overview
3	4-IPBES_TCA_CH2_DMR 2.7_ILK_invitations_V2(A)	pdf		Emails used to invite potential contributors